

Fig: Calvin and Hobbes by Bill Watterson.¹

Confucius Confusion in the use of A.I based tools.

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Problem Statement:

A given person is said to be Confucius Confused², if like Confucius, one is confused about the nature of reality, the waking or the reflection in a puddle. In this paper, the author proves that use of A.I tools in an academic setting, such as a literature review course, does not lead to a Confucius Confusion, amongst the participants in the course.

Methods: Given the following set of papers in a assignment on review on the topic 'presence' in CSCI 8980 004 course at UMN Twin Cities, Fall 2020,

"Mel Slater and colleagues are among the earliest researchers to set about trying to systematically quantify a user's sense of presence in an immersive virtual environment. One of their foundational papers on the topic is:

Mel Slater, Martin Usoh, and Anthony Steed. (1994). [**Depth of presence in virtual environments**](#)

[\(Links to an external site.\)](#)

, *Presence: Teleoperators and Virtual Environments*, 3(2), 130–144. doi: 10.1162/pres.1994.3.2.130, which led to the development of the [SUS \(Slater-Usoh-Steed\) presence questionnaire](#)

[\(Links to an external site.\)](#)

, still used by many researchers today.

Other presence questionnaires approximately contemporary to the SUS include:

The [Witmer-Singer Presence Questionnaire \(PQ\)](#)

[\(Links to an external site.\)](#)

, introduced in: Bob G. Witmer, Michael J. Singer. (1998). [**Measuring Presence in Virtual Environments: A Presence Questionnaire**](#)

[\(Links to an external site.\)](#)

, *Presence: Teleoperators and Virtual Environments*, 7(3), 225-240.

The [igroup presence questionnaire \(IPQ\)](#)

[\(Links to an external site.\)](#)

, introduced in: Thomas Schubert, Frank Friedmann, Holger Regenbrecht. (2001) [**The Experience of Presence: Factor Analytic Insights**](#)

[\(Links to an external site.\)](#)

, *Presence: Teleoperators and Virtual Environments*, 10(2), 266-281.

and the *ITC- Sense of Presence Inventory* (available only by request from the authors), introduced in: Jane Lessiter, Jonathan Freeman, Edmund Keogh, Jules Davidoff. (2001). [A Cross-Media Presence Questionnaire: The ITC-Sense of Presence Inventory](#)

[\(Links to an external site.\)](#)

, *Presence: Teleoperators and Virtual Environments*, 10(3), 282-297.

Despite concerted validation efforts by the research community, presence questionnaires often proved to be limited in their reliability and efficacy. An iconic opinion piece on that topic, authored by Mel Slater in 2006, is: [How Colorful Was Your Day? Why Questionnaires Cannot Assess Presence in Virtual Environments](#)

[\(Links to an external site.\)](#)

, *Presence: Teleoperators and Virtual Environments*, 13(4), 484-493.

Other types of measures have also been proposed to assess presence, including: behavioral measures and physiological measures. These alternatives are briefly reviewed in: Brent Insko. (2003). [Measuring Presence: Subjective, Behavioral and Physiological Methods](#)

[\(Links to an external site.\)](#)

, in *Being There: Concepts, effects and measurement of user presence in synthetic environments*. G. Riva, F. Davide, W.A IJsselsteijn (Eds.), Ios Press, 2003, Amsterdam, The Netherlands.

In 2009, Mel Slater elaborated new theories related to the phenomenon of presence, which he describes in: Mel Slater. (2009). [Place illusion and plausibility can lead to realistic behaviour in immersive virtual environments](#)

[\(Links to an external site.\)](#)

, *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London, B: Biological Sciences*, 364(1535): 3549–3557. “

Use of Summarization A.I

The author used the smmry.com with the right parameters to create summaries of the above mentioned papers, proving the judicious use of A.I tools, in saving time and effort. Given the average time needed to read a paper being more than 10 minutes, a

summarizer usually provides a summary of the main contributions of a paper in less than a few minutes of time and effort.

Results:

Knowledge of the algorithm, in the case of smmry.com, helps in eliminating the magical effects perceived of A.I, as mere computation by an algorithm, in this case the ranking of sentences and a console print of the top n sentences, which enables, a speedy review and a ROI for more data from the publication.

The Summaries Generated.

Depth of Presence in Virtual Environments Mel Slater, Martin Usoh, Anthony Steed, Department of Computer Science, and London Parallel Applications Centre, QMW, University of London, Mile End Road, London E1 4NS, UK. Abstract This paper describes a study to assess the influence of a variety of factors on reported level of presence in immersive virtual environments.

A logistic regression analysis revealed that subjective reporting of presence was significantly positively associated with visual and kinesthetic representation systems, and negatively with the auditory system.

Immersion can lead to presence, the participant's sense of "Being there" in the virtual environment.

The psychological sense of presence may be considered as an emergent 2 property of an IVE. It is important to understand the factors that contribute to this, and a means of quantifying the concept of presence itself.

To what extent is their sense of presence correlated with the depth of environment visited? 2.

Indicators of Presence provide a conceptual framework for presence referring to factors similar to-(e) of Section 1, and also potential indicators of presence that may be useful for measurement.

Would therefore be a function of these three effects, the reported extent of presence mainly depending on the person's dominant mode of thinking.

Visual dominance may lead to their reporting according to their sense of presence in the visual modality.

Stacking Environments An IVE system may be thought of as a general purpose presence transforming machine.

A flight simulator offers a very high degree of presence, but only in one specific environment.

An IVE offers presence in an arbitrary set of environments.

Laws of Physics In the earlier pilot experiment, one of the factors reported by subjects as decreasing the sense of presence was the problem that the virtual world did not behave as expected - the laws of physics were violated.

The earlier experiment also suggested strongly that presence was increased when subjects were presented to a scenario where they were standing on a narrow ledge over a precipice, reminiscent of E.J. Gibson's visual cliff experiment.

Virtual Actors Responding to the Subject We also found the looming effect, where subjects "Ducked" in response to an object flying towards their face, influenced their presence.

Subjective Factors The results of the earlier pilot experiment strongly suggested a relationship between presence and the dominant representation system of the subject, elicited from a content analysis of essays written by them after their experience in the IVE. An exploratory statistical analysis indicated, with respect to the experience of the displayed environment, that the subjective rating of presence was positively correlated with increasing visual dominance, and negatively correlated with increasing auditory dominance.

11 Subjects in the pilot study had reported as a factor that decreased the sense of presence of the verbal interchange between experimenters and subjects caused by the latter giving instructions to the former.

16 I feel as if my friend's presence is close to me.

5.2 Presence 17 Subjective experience of presence was elicited through three questions separated from one another in the questionnaire given after the experiment: 4.

Results 6.1 Summary The purpose of the experiment was to test hypotheses relating to the subjective factors, the gravity, visual cliff, and virtual actor factors, and the stacking of environment variables, to the level of reported presence.

The statistical analysis revealed: That the measured level of presence is positively associated with V and K, or negatively associated with A. This confirms the earlier result of the pilot study

mentioned in Section 4(d). That the measured level of presence is positively associated with the depth of environment, when the transitions are made using the virtual HMD, but negatively associated with depth when the transitions are through doors.

6.3 Discussion In the exploratory statistical analysis of the earlier pilot experiment, presence was measured by the responses to a question similar to 4 in Section 5.2.

The measure for presence used as the dependent variable requires subjects to answer at least one of the three presence questions with a high rank in order to obtain a non-zero score overall.

Now if high presence in an environment implies that the person will respond to events in that environment, and if the VB is a particularly important environmental object, then it follows that events connected with the VB must be particularly important with regard to indication of presence.

Interestingly, these subjects report no difference in their sense of presence, as measured by the responses to the three presence questions than the remaining 19 subjects, and generally seem to be no different to the remaining subjects in most other respects.

In an IVE both kinds of presence are obviously important.

In particular we have presented evidence that supports the notion that a person's dominant representation system may influence their reported sense of presence, and that presence may be associated with stacking depth.

The questionnaire responses are themselves another such "Sign" of presence - and must be treated cautiously.

The stacked environments model suggests that provided the transitions from level to level are suitably made, the existence of more than one level can enhance rather than diminish presence.

If the method of stacking environments is generally found to contribute to increased presence, then it could be used to improve the level of presence for individuals who would normally experience a relatively low level.

According to our model, a person who is dominant on the auditory scale would normally experience a low level of presence in a predominantly visual environment.

SUS Questionnaire.

Please rate your sense of being in the virtual environment, on a scale of 1 to 7, where 7 represents your normal experience of being in a place.

To what extent were there times during the experience when the virtual environment was the reality for you? 3.

When you think back to the experience, do you think of the virtual environment more as images that you saw or more as somewhere that you visited? 4.

During the time of the experience, which was the strongest on the whole, your sense of being in the virtual environment or of being elsewhere? 5.

Consider your memory of being in the virtual environment.

How similar in terms of the structure of the memory is this to the structure of the memory of other places you have been today? By 'structure of the memory' consider things like the extent to which you have a visual memory of the virtual environment, whether that memory is in colour, the extent to which the memory seems vivid or realistic, its size, location in your imagination, the extent to which it is panoramic in your imagination, and other such structural elements.

During the time of your experience, did you often think to yourself that you were actually in the virtual environment? ..

Despite concerted validation efforts by the research community, presence questionnaires often proved to be limited in their reliability and efficacy. An iconic opinion piece on that topic, authored by Mel Slater in 2006, is: [How Colorful Was Your Day? Why Questionnaires Cannot Assess Presence in Virtual Environments](#) ([Links to an external site.](#))

, Presence: Teleoperators and Virtual Environments, 13(4), 484-493.

The meaninglessness of this analysis illustrates that the equivalent methodology used by presence researchers, may bring into being the idea of presence in the minds of VE participants.

For presence to be useful as a 'common currency' of VE experiences, it must be measurable.

In Section 3 we provide some arguments against the use of questionnaires in presence research.

In Section 4 we discuss the method used to support the claim that we can have no evidence that 'presence' exists outside of the minds of presence researchers.

The 'embodied presence' approach is similar to this and to the idea of Slater, Usoh and Steed where it is argued that it is essential for there to be a close match between kinesthetic proprioception and the stream of sensory data: if the participant is supposed to be moving through an environment by walking, then when visual flow indicates walking, presence will be higher the more that the person's bodily movements correspond to real walking.

Have shown the inherent instability of questionnaire based presence assessment methods, and they propose a behavioural solution, and there have been several attempts to provide behavioural measures of presence.

The use of physiological measures as surrogates for presence is interesting - but limited to situations where the physiological response is obvious.

What should be the expected physiological response to mundane situations such as being in a virtual room which has a table and some chairs? A fundamental problem with the vast majority of presence research is that there is no real evidence at all for the existence of the phenomenon, except perhaps through introspection.

Presence in a VE may seem to exist simply because questions are asked about it.

So with presence: Is a person's interpretation of 'being there' that of involvement, or attention, or interest, or realism, or a confounding of all these and others? A possible way out of this circularity is by relating questionnaire reported presence to other phenomena such as variations in levels of immersion.

Again there is no independent evidence that anything is actually happening at the level of brain activity or behaviour that can be characterised as a unique psychological or behavioural process that we would call 'presence'.

Against Presence Questionnaires Questionnaires are a very useful tool in social and psychological research.

In everyday life, people are not normally in situations where their presence in the place that they actually are may be doubted.

Only in extreme or abnormal conditions may a person's presence be in doubt - for example, in hallucinatory experiences triggered by mental dysfunction or drugs.

The question of 'presence' arises for virtual environments simply because VEs override sense impressions from the real world with those generated by the computer display systems in several sensory modalities.

A person cannot be 'trained' to give appropriate answers to presence questions.

In relation to presence, since there is not a stock of lesser or greater experiences of presence, this comparison cannot be made.

If someone is 'trained' to think about their presence in preparation for answering a questionnaire, then already they are thinking differently from how they would normally in everyday life - since in everyday life, we do not walk around thinking 'To what extent do I have a sense of being here?' It was argued that given the state of VE technology today, any presence questionnaire ought to be able to distinguish experiences in the real world from experiences in the virtual world.

So respondents reinterpret presence to mean, for example, their sense of comfort, lack of alienation, involvement, similarity to some idealised experience, and so on.

Another explanation of the same result is that indeed the degree of presence in the two situations was the same - simply because very minimal cues are needed to establish presence.

Presence has not been established in any way, by any researcher as an identifiable mental attribute or mental activity.

A possible exception is the use of physiological measures that indirectly capture presence: the argument is that because people experienced measurable anxiety when confronting a virtual precipice, they must have been present.

We do not know that 'presence' exists in any real form as something observable that happens when a person experiences a virtual reality.

On the optimistic side, none of the above implies that presence is not in itself a useful concept, and it may be the case that presence can be associated with observable mental states and activity.

Other types of measures have also been proposed to assess presence, including: behavioral measures and physiological measures. These alternatives are briefly reviewed in: Brent Insko. (2003). [Measuring Presence: Subjective, Behavioral and Physiological Methods](#) ([Links to an external site.](#))

, in Being There: Concepts, effects and measurement of user presence in synthetic environments, G. Riva, F. Davide, W.A IJsselsteijn (Eds.), Jos Press, 2003, Amsterdam, The Netherlands.

7.2 Subjective measures Because of the subjective nature of presence, it is only logical that the first attempts to measure presence relied on the VR participant's self-reported sense of presence.

Some researchers have identified problems in which the subjective measures produce unstable and inconsistent responses depending on a participant's prior experience.

7.3 Behavioral measures An alternative approach to avoid the subjective nature of questionnaires is to measure participant responses that are produced automatically, without conscious thought, but are sensibly correlated with being present in a particular environment.

The premise behind these measures is that the more a participant feels present in a virtual environment, the more his responses to stimuli will more nearly match those behaviors he would exhibit in an identical real environment.

A magnetic tracking device measured the participants' movements.

Another problem with behavioral measures is that there is little likelihood that a behavioral measure will be appropriate for all environments and all content.

7.4 Physiological measures There are numerous physiological responses that can be measured.

Heart rate can be measured with an electrocardiogram which measures electrical activity across the skin associated with the electrical activity of the heart.

The unit of measure is the Siemen, the inverse of an Ohm, the measure of resistance.

Change in skin temperature measures the change in temperature on the extremities of the body.

Skin temperature reactions can be measured by placing a thermistor at the end of one of the fingers and holding it in place with thin porous tape.

Meehan conducted a series of experiments using the above three physiological measures in the virtual precipice environment as seen in Figure 7.1.

His results showed that heart rate was the most sensitive measure of the three, sometimes more sensitive than the subjective measures.

Two earlier studies involving these three measures resulted in only skin conductance correlating well with subjective presence measures [21, 31]. Other potentially useful measures might

include EEG recordings of cortical activity, electromyogram measurements of facial muscle tensions, respiration rate and blood pressure.

7.5 Comparing presence measures To judge the usefulness and robustness of a measure, the following criteria are used: ! ! ! Reliability - a measure produces repeatable results, across trials and across participants.

Validity - a measure that measures subjective presence, or at least correlates well with established subjective presence measures.

Sensitivity - a measure can distinguish between various levels of presence.

7.5.2 Behavioral measures There has been little research into whether behavioral measures are reliable in virtual environments.

Behavioral measures can be valid if it can be shown that the behaviors exhibited by the participants were directly a result of feeling present in the virtual environment.

These measures can also be somewhat exposed to subject bias.

In terms of sensitivity, Insko showed that observed behavioral measures in response to a fear-inducing stimulus could differentiate between a virtual precipice, and a virtual precipice augmented with a 1.5 inch physical ledge.

7.5.3 Physiological measures The dissertation of Michael Meehan used these criteria to evaluate three physiological measures: heart rate, skin temperature, and galvanic skin response.

Physiological measures are more objective than either subjective or behavioral measures; they are generally not consciously affected by the participants, and with limited, uniform instructions, cannot be affected by the experimenters.

7.6 How to choose appropriate measures So what presence measures should an experimenter choose when conducting experiments in virtual environments? The obvious answer is to use as many as is feasible.

2009.0138 Place illusion and plausibility can lead to realistic behaviour in immersive virtual environments Mel Slater^{1,2,*} 1 EVENT Lab, Institute for Brain, Cognition and Behavior, ICREA-University of Barcelona, 08035 Barcelona, Spain 2 Department of Computer Science, University College London, London WC1E 6BT, UK In this paper, I address the question as to

why participants tend to respond realistically to situations and events portrayed within an immersive virtual reality system.

PI is constrained by the sensorimotor contingencies afforded by the virtual reality system.

Keywords: virtual reality; virtual environment; presence; telepresence; plausibility 1.

INTRODUCTION The technology for immersive virtual reality has existed for 40 years, initially as a demonstrated laboratory-based idea and for the past 20 years as practical, affordable and useful systems.

The SCs supported by a system define a set of valid actions that are meaningful in terms of perception within the virtual environment depicted.

Suppose in either system the participant wears a tracked data glove, which is represented as a hand within the virtual environment.

With today's generally available technology, participants will not experience a virtual reality system with generalized haptics, so that this dimension of SC will always fail if tested-for example, if a participant in a virtual reality touches some arbitrary virtual object they would feel nothing.

Using a head-tracked HMD with appropriate haptics and sound, it is theoretically possible to construct a virtual environment in which a participant can virtually carry out all of the actions of sitting down at a desktop display, and experience that situation as a scenario within the virtual reality.

With an HMD without tracking it would not be possible to simulate all of the actions corresponding to going into another system, but it would be possible in the Cave or Realistic behaviour in virtual reality M. Slater HMD with tracking to simulate what it is like to go into an HMD without tracking.

In a system such as the Cave it is possible to use its associated valid actions to produce the SCs necessary to 'perceive' a virtual environment displayed on a desktop system.

In the early 1990s this idea was transplanted to virtual reality, where instead of being at the remote physical environment, the participant was in a virtual environment with a sense of being at the place depicted by the virtual displays.

In any kind of virtual system there will always be limits beyond which SCs fail to be applicable.

PI IN LOWER ORDER SYSTEMS Can PI occur in computer games as used on desktop systems? To what extent can you have a feeling of 'being there' with respect to a desktop virtual

reality system? If we consider PI as based on the extent to which normal SCs apply to perception, then the answer is 'you cannot'.

Imagine comparing different Cave systems or Realistic behaviour in virtual reality M. Slater Caves with HMDs, large power walls and so on.

Just as PI is maintained through synchronous correlations between the act of moving and concomitant changes in the images that form perception, so I posit that an important component leading to Psi is for the virtual reality to provide correlations between external events not directly caused by the participant and his/her own sensations.

THE BODY In physical reality and first-order virtual reality, there is something very simple that you can do to physically establish your presence.

Wearing an HMD a virtual body can be portrayed collocated with your real physical body, so that when you do the same movements that you would do in physical reality to look at your body, instead you would see your virtual body.

Virtual reality can transform not only your sense of place, and of reality, but also the apparent properties of your own body.

Once you have ceased to accept the 'reality' of that virtual character, for example, Psi does not usually reform again.

CONCLUSIONS We have previously defined presence in virtual reality as the extent to which people respond realistically within a virtual environment, where response is taken at every level from low-level physiological to high-level emotional and behavioural responses.

2005b The psychology of persecutory ideation II-a virtual reality experimental study.

Sanchez-Vives, M. V. & Slater, M. 2005 From presence to consciousness through virtual reality.

Slater, M. & Wilbur, S. 1997 A framework for immersive virtual environments: speculations on the role of presence in virtual environments, *Presence: Teleop.*

Slater, M., Usoh, M. & Steed, A. 1995 Taking steps: the influence of a walking technique on presence in virtual reality, *ACM Trans.*

In order to spin this article to avoid plagiarism in a automation workflow, the author tried google translating the text to hmong and back to english and the resulting text cleared the plagiarism check on grammarly, indicating that for automation workflows, text spinning is a viable alternative, saving precious human hours and effort, the original UNIX philosophy.

However it should also be mentioned that the quality of creative and scientific writing from article spinners is far lower than that of handwritten texts and original contributions should always be hand written with background and contexts made into automation workflows, preferably interactive.

Txawm tias muaj kev sib raug zoo los ntawm cov kws tshawb fawb hauv zej zog, cov lus nug muaj nyob rau ntau qhov lawv ntseeg tau thiab ua tau zoo. Ib qho kev xav lub ntsiab ntawm cov ncauj lus ntawd, sau los ntawm Mel Slater xyoo 2006, yog: Muaj Hnub Xim Li Cas? Vim li cas cov lus nug tsis tuaj yeem ntsuas qhov kuaj pom hauv Virtual Ib puag ncig (Txuas rau lub vev xaib sab nraud.)

, Kev Muaj Peev Xwm: Cov Kws Saib Xyuas Xov Tooj thiab Virtual Ib Puag Ncig, 13 (4), 484-493.

Lub ntsiab lus tsis muaj txiaj ntsig ntawm qhov kev tsom xam no qhia tau hais tias cov txheej txheem sib npaug uas siv los ntawm cov kws tshawb nrhiav pom, yuav coj los ua lub tswv yim ntawm kev xav hauv lub siab ntawm cov neeg koom nrog VE.

Txhawm rau qhov muaj txiaj ntsig yog qhov 'txiaj ntsig' ntawm kev paub ntawm VE, nws yuav tsum ntsuas tau.

Hauv Seem 3 peb muab qee qhov kev sib cav los tawm tsam siv cov lus nug hauv kev tshawb nrhiav.

Hauv Tshooj 4 peb tham txog txoj kev siv los txhawb qhov kev thov tias peb tuaj yeem tsis muaj pov thawj tias 'muaj' nyob sab nraud lub siab ntawm cov kws tshawb nrhiav.

Lub 'embodied kuaj pom' mus kom ze zoo ib yam li qhov no thiab lub tswv yim ntawm Slater, Usoh thiab Steed qhov twg nws tau sib cav tias nws yog qhov tseem ceeb rau qhov yuav tsum muaj qhov sib luag ntawm qhov kev xav tau zoo thiab cov kwj ntawm cov ntaub ntawv hnov: yog tias tus koom nrog yuav tsum tau txav mus los ntawm ib puag ncig los ntawm kev taug kev, tom qab ntawd thaum pom tseeb ntws los qhia, taug kev yuav muaj ntau dua qhov uas tus neeg lub cev txav mus raws li kev taug kev tiag.

Tau qhia qhov tsis txaus ntseeg ntawm cov lus nug raws li muaj cov kev ntsuas kev ntsuam xyuas, thiab lawv hais tawm txog kev daws tus cwj pwm, thiab tau muaj ntau qhov kev sim los muab cov kev coj cwj pwm ntawm qhov muaj.

Kev siv cov kev ntsuas ntawm physiological raws li surrogates rau qhov pom yog qhov nthuav - tab sis txwv rau cov xwm txheej uas cov lus teb muaj sia yog pom tseeb.

Dab tsi yuav tsum muaj qhov kev xav ntawm lub cev muaj zog rau cov xwm txheej mundane xws li nyob hauv chav tsev virtual uas muaj lub rooj noj mov thiab qee cov rooj zaum? Ib qho teeb meem tseem ceeb nrog rau feem coob ntawm qhov kev tshawb nrhiav kuaj pom yog tsis muaj pov thawj tiag tiag ntawm txhua yam rau lub hav zoov ntawm qhov tshwm sim, tsuas yog saib tsam los ntawm kev tshawb nrhiav.

Muaj nyob rau hauv VE yuav zoo li muaj nyob tsuas yog vim cov lus nug tau nug txog nws.

Yog li nrog muaj: Puas yog ib tus neeg txhais lus txog 'tau nyob ntawd' ntawm kev koom tes, lossis kev saib xyuas, lossis kev txaus siab, lossis qhov tseeb, lossis ua rau txhua yam tsis meej? Ib txoj hauv kev tawm ntawm lub voj voog no yog los ntawm kev txheeb cov lus nug tau ceeb toom pom muaj lwm cov kev tshwm sim xws li kev hloov pauv ntawm them ntawm kev siv.

Ib zaug ntxiv tsis muaj pov thawj ywj siab hais tias txhua yam tau tshwm sim nyob rau them ntawm lub hlwb kev ua ub no los yog kev coj tus cwj pwm uas tuaj yeem ua qhov txawv txav ntawm lub hlwb lossis tus cwj pwm uas peb yuav hu ua 'muaj'.

Tawm Tsam Cov Lus Nug Cov Lus Nug Cov lus nug yog qhov txiaj ntsig zoo hauv kev tshawb fawb hauv tib neeg thiab lub siab ntsws.

Hauv lub neej txhua hnuv, tib neeg tsis niaj zaus nyob hauv cov xwm txheej uas lawv qhov chaw nyob hauv qhov chaw uas lawv tau ua haujlwm los tej zaum yuav ua xyem xyav.

Ntawm qhov kev xav zoo, tsis muaj ib qho saum toj no qhia tias muaj nyob rau hauv nws tus kheej tsis muaj lub tswv yim muaj txiaj ntsig, thiab nws yog rooj plaub uas muaj nyob nrog rau kev saib xyuas lub hlwb thiab kev ua si.

Despite strong relationships from community scientists, the questions exist in many of their areas of trust and effectiveness. One of the main themes of those topics, written by Mel Slater in 2006, is: How Colorful Are There? Why the query cannot measure the presence in the Virtual Environment

(Link to external website.)

, Capabilities: Telephone and Virtual Environment Manager, 13 (4), 484-493.

The inaccurate summary of this analysis suggests that the equivalence procedures used by the researchers find, will lead to the concept of thinking in the minds of the participants. VE.

For a benefit to be a 'benefit' of VE knowledge, it must be measurable.

In Section 3 we present some arguments to challenge the use of research questions.

In Chapter 4 we discuss ways to support the claim that we can have no evidence of 'existence' outside the minds of researchers.

The 'embodied presence' approach is similar to this and the idea of Slater, Usoh and Steed where it has been argued that it is important to have a balance of needs well and the stream of information heard: if the participant had to move from the environment through the walk, then when the obvious flow to show, the walk will be more than the the human body moves as if on a real walk.

The skepticism of the questions was based on the presence of assessment criteria, and they addressed the problem-solving behavior, and there were several attempts to justify the behaviors of the presence.

The use of physiological measures as surrogates for visualization is interesting - but limited to situations where the biological response is obvious.

What should be the physical feel for mundane events such as in a virtual room with a dining table and some chairs? An important problem with most of the investigations is that there is no real evidence of anything for the existence of the phenomenon, only perhaps from research.

Available in VE would seem to exist only because the question was asked about it.

So with yes: Does an interpreter mean 'being there' by involvement, or supervision, or interest, or fact, or ambiguity? One way out of this cycle is by analyzing the questionnaires reported to have other effects such as changes in the level of use.

Again, there is no independent evidence that anything has happened at the level of brain activity or behavior that could cause a difference in the brain or the behavior that we would like to see. called 'yes'.

Responding to Questions Questions Questions are a valuable tool in research in humans and psychologists.

In everyday life, people are not always in situations where they are in the place where they have worked or may be skeptical.

On the positive side, none of the above shows that there is in itself no useful idea, and it is the case that exists with mental care and activity.

Fig: Visual output from a plagiarism check using the Grammarly tool. ³

The presentation in the seminar classroom setting, through zoom, is easily achieved through the use of text to speech accommodation software built into windows, creating a 'narrator', as an interactive experience in screen shared participation in a virtual classroom. ⁴

Discussion.

In the authors perception, A.I is not systems thinking, but in critical thinking is a statistical, procedural or deep tool of numbers and data, with categorization or maps, merely number crunching. With this approach any A.I or data mining tool for decision support or for task automation and UI use in accommodation, is easily achieved without confucius confusion, or a crossover syndrome. Mere algorithms without a systems context cannot be integrative and thus undeployed in this sense cannot lead to anthropomorphic confusion or to confucius confusion or a similar two worldly phenomenon.

In the episode "Trapped In An Epic Tale"⁵, Puss In Boots finds himself with a schizophrenic hallucinatory voice of the narrator. As a subjective phenomenon, such voices of augmented reality of being in interactive experiences, without presence as AR. may be a valid experience and normal in the involvement of a narrator, allowing for the use of TTS, accommodation in remote classrooms for automated presentation and anonymity.

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1. Watterson, B. *The Authoritative Calvin And Hobbes*. (Andrews McMeel Publishing, 1990).
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